

THEME OF REVENGE IN THE NOVELS OF HERMAN MELVILLE

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ANNOTATION: The article below gives data about works by H. Melville, his writing style and elements of revenge in his novels.

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Herman Melville is an American novelist and short story writer best known for Moby Dick. Along with his contemporaries Nathaniel Hawthorne, Walt Whitman, and the New England Transcendentalists, Melville is one of the most critically acclaimed and widely read American writers of the 19th century. In addition, he was a famous American writer who lived a difficult life. His life was full of ups and downs, and his legacy continues to inspire readers and writers. In his youth - a traveler, in the middle of his life - a famous and respected writer, in his maturity - a forgotten civil servant. Melville's early life was greatly influenced by his family's financial difficulties.

The distinctive features of Melville's story are its deep philosophical themes, complex artistic symbolism and synthetic. G. Melville is a romantic and an American, closely connected with social life, with the ideological and artistic thinking of his country and his time - romantic humanism. His writing is completely romantic in style and style: the most complex images and symbols directly return to the concepts of the romantic philosophy of existence. As for the unique universality of the voice, the cosmopolitanism of his best works, this is undoubtedly a characteristic of genius. In Melville's works, the widespread Transcendentalist ideas, which look for support and hope in the human heart, have also become a polemic: where the Transcendentalists saw light and hope in the human soul, Melville notes its cruelty and darkness. Many of his works cover the topics of human nature, morality, the struggle for self-awareness and autonomy, and the search for the meaning and purpose of life. Although revenge is not a central theme in all of Melville's works, it does feature prominently in some of his novels. The theme of revenge serves as a catalyst for character development and moral reflection in Melville's narratives. Two of his most famous works dealing with the theme of revenge are Moby-Dick and Benito Sereno. It should be noted that while revenge is an important theme in these novels, Melville's wider work is known for exploring other themes such as human nature, the search for meaning, and the complexities of good and evil. Melville's literary legacy continued to grow in the years after his death. He is now recognized as one of the greatest American writers of the 19th century. His works are often studied and celebrated for their innovative style and themes that explore complex questions about human nature, society, and the meaning of life.

In some of Melville's works, revenge is shown as a rightful response to injustice. For example, in the novel Benito Sereno, the main character, Captain Delano, seeks revenge against the slave rebellion led by Benito Sereno. However, as the story progresses, Delano discovers that Cereno is actually a slave forced into his position by rebel captors. In this way, Melville challenges the reader's assumptions about revenge and justice, suggesting that revenge is not

always a valid response to wrongdoing. In both *Moby-Dick* and *Benito Sereno*, Melville examines the destructive nature of revenge. He delves deep into the psychological complexities of characters who hunger for revenge and explores the moral and ethical implications of such pursuits. Melville's exploration of revenge goes beyond simple notions of justice and portrays it as a force that corrupts the human soul and has tragic consequences.

Melville also explores the theme of revenge in his novel *Pierre*, in which he tells the story of a young man who discovers that his father has secretly married his mother's sister, making him the product of inbreeding. Pierre's desire to avenge his father and aunt leads him to make a series of impulsive and disastrous decisions. Through the character of Pierre, Melville presents revenge as a destructive force that leads to moral corruption and self-destruction. Another work of Melville that reflects the theme of revenge is "*Billy Budd*". In this novella, John Claggart's character develops a deep hatred for the innocent and virtuous Billy Budd. Claggart's jealousy and desire for revenge lead him to falsely accuse Budd of the rebellion, with tragic consequences for both characters. Melville examines the corrosive power of revenge and the tragic results it can provoke. Melville's exploration of revenge can be traced back to his early writings, such as his first novel, *Typee* (1846). In this novel, the main character, Tommo, seeks revenge on a local citizen who stole his knife. However, the act of revenge ultimately leads to Tommo's moral decline and self-destruction. This theme of revenge leading to moral corruption and self-destruction is further explored in Melville's later works.

In these works, Melville uses the theme of revenge to explore the complex motivations and emotions that drive people to seek revenge, as well as the often disastrous consequences that result from this pursuit. Through his characters and stories, Melville offers a thought-provoking commentary on the destructive nature of revenge and the human condition. In conclusion, Herman Melville's concept of revenge is complex and multifaceted. Through his novels, Melville explores the destructive power of revenge, as well as its potential for moral corruption and self-destruction. At the same time, it presents revenge as a just response to injustice and challenges the reader's assumption that revenge consists of just and unjust forms.

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